

Factors Influencing Nurses' Adherence to Standard Operational Procedures For Preventing Patient Falls

Lailatu Rohmah*¹, Diansanto Prayoga²

Faculty of Health, Medicine, and Natural Sciences, Airlangga University

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received June 19, 2025

Revised June 21, 2025

Accepted June 28, 2025

Available online July 10, 2025

Kata kunci:

Kepatuhan Perawat, SOP, Pencegahan Jatuh

Keywords:

Nurse Compliance, Standard Operational Procedures, Fall Prevention

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.
Copyright © 2025 by Author. Published by Yayasan Daarul Huda

ABSTRAK

Risiko jatuh merupakan salah satu insiden keselamatan pasien yang paling sering terjadi di rumah sakit dan telah menjadi perhatian global dalam upaya peningkatan mutu pelayanan kesehatan. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengidentifikasi dan menganalisis faktor-faktor yang memengaruhi kepatuhan perawat terhadap prosedur operasional standar (SOP) pencegahan jatuh di lingkungan rumah sakit. Penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan tinjauan pustaka dengan mengkaji artikel-artikel dari basis data daring terpercaya. Tiga artikel relevan dianalisis, dan mengungkapkan bahwa faktor-faktor seperti sikap, pengetahuan, tingkat pendidikan, usia, beban kerja, lama pengalaman kerja, ketersediaan fasilitas, dan peran kepala perawat berhubungan signifikan dengan kepatuhan perawat terhadap SOP. Perawat dengan sikap dan pengetahuan positif, latar belakang pendidikan tinggi, dan lingkungan kerja yang suportif cenderung menunjukkan kepatuhan yang lebih tinggi terhadap SOP pencegahan jatuh. Kepatuhan perawat terhadap SOP pencegahan jatuh dipengaruhi oleh berbagai faktor. Oleh karena itu, rumah sakit perlu menerapkan intervensi komprehensif untuk meningkatkan kepatuhan dan keselamatan pasien.

ABSTRACT

Fall risk is one of the most frequently occurring patient safety incidents in hospitals and has become a global concern in efforts to improve the quality of healthcare services. This study aims to identify and analyze the factors that influence nurses' compliance with standard operational procedures for fall prevention in hospital settings. The study employed a literature review approach by examining articles from reputable online databases. Three relevant articles were analyzed, revealing that factors such as attitude, knowledge, educational level, age, workload, length of work experience, availability of facilities, and the role of the head nurse are significantly associated with nurses' compliance with standard operational procedures. Nurses with positive attitudes and knowledge, higher educational backgrounds, and supportive work environments tend to demonstrate higher adherence to fall prevention SOP. Nurses' compliance with fall prevention standard operational procedures is influenced by multiple factors. Therefore, hospitals need to implement comprehensive interventions to enhance adherence and patient safety.

INTRODUCTION

Patient safety, as stipulated in the Indonesian Hospital Law No. 44 of 2009 Article 3, is a top priority in healthcare services. It encompasses a hospital's obligation to ensure safe care through processes such as risk assessment, patient identification, incident reporting and analysis, risk management, learning from events, and implementing corrective actions to reduce potential harm (BPK RI, 2009). It is estimated that 10–25% of hospitalized patients experience safety-related incidents, which may lead to physical or psychological harm, financial loss, and reputational damage to the hospital (Fajarini *et al.*, 2024).

According to the Joint Commission International (JCI), one of the primary goals of patient safety is to prevent falls. A report documented 52 fall-related incidents across 11 healthcare facilities in five countries (Fajarini *et al.*, 2024). The Indonesian Ministry of Health Regulation No. 11 of 2017 also emphasizes fall prevention as a critical aspect of patient safety. Surveys show that the global prevalence of patient falls reaches up to 30%. WHO data indicates that adverse events among hospitalized patients range from 3% to 16% globally. Incident reporting plays a crucial role in problem identification and facilitates organizational learning. However, Indonesia currently lacks precise national data on patient falls. Falls remain one of the most common patient safety incidents—second only to medication errors. A report from the 12th PERSI Congress stated that 34 cases, or 14% of all hospital incidents, were related to falls (Fajarini *et al.*, 2024), highlighting that current fall prevention measures have not been optimally implemented.

*Corresponding author

Email: lailatu.rohmah-2021@fkm.unair.ac.id

Hospitals have established standard operational procedures for fall prevention, which must be followed by all healthcare personnel, particularly nurses. As frontline caregivers, nurses play a strategic role in fall risk screening, environmental monitoring, educating patients and families, and implementing preventive measures. Despite this, compliance levels among nurses vary considerably, and in some cases, lapses in adherence have contributed to fall incidents. Several factors are known to influence nurse compliance, including predisposing, enabling, and reinforcing elements (Alfisenna *et al.*, 2024), such as workload, knowledge of fall risk management, and institutional support through training and assistive tools (Fajarini *et al.*, 2024).

Numerous studies have identified factors that affect nurses' adherence to fall prevention standard operational procedures for preventing patient falls. Understanding these variables is essential to design effective interventions that can improve service quality and ensure patient safety. Therefore, this study aims to explore and analyze the determinants of nurse compliance in implementing fall prevention protocols, providing a foundation for policy improvement and better clinical practice in hospital settings.

METHODS

This research employs a literature review approach aimed at identifying and analyzing findings from previous studies on the factors influencing nurses' compliance with standard operational procedures for fall risk prevention in patients. Articles were retrieved from reputable academic databases, including Google Scholar, Garuda Journal, and Semantic Scholar, focusing on publications from 2020 to 2025 that were accessible in full text. Search terms included combinations of keywords such as "Nurse Compliance," "standard operational procedures," and "Fall Risk Prevention in Patients." Boolean operators (AND, OR) were utilized to broaden the scope and precision of the search results. The selection process was conducted in stages, beginning with title and abstract screening, followed by full-text evaluation. Eligible articles were further analyzed using a structured data extraction process, recorded in a spreadsheet to identify emerging themes and categorize influencing factors. The findings from each study were compiled into a summary table and synthesized to highlight consistent patterns as well as any conflicting results across the literature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are the search results, 6 related articles were found that are relevant:

No	Author and year of publication	Title	Methods	Result
1.	Siti Fatonah, Idawati Manurung Ade Putri Aulia (2023)	Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kepatuhan Perawat Dalam Melaksanakan Standar Oprasional Pencegahan Risiko Jatuh Di Rsud Dr.H. Abdul Moeloek Provinsi Lampung	Penelitian ini adalah penelitian kuantitatif, desain penelitian analitik menggunakan pendekatan <i>cross sectional</i>	Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa terdapat hubungan antara sikap, Tingkat Pendidikan, dan lama kerja, dengan kepatuhan perawat dalam melaksanakan SPO pencegahan pasien risiko jatuh.
2.	Alfisenna, Erwin, Yulia Rizka (2024)	Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kepatuhan Perawat Dalam Pelaksanaan Standar Operasional Pasien Risiko Jatuh	Penelitian ini mengadopsi desain analisis korelasional kuantitatif dengan pendekatan <i>cross-sectional</i> menggunakan teknik <i>stratified random sampling</i>	Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa faktor usia, lama bekerja, kesadaran diri, dan penilaian terhadap fasilitas memiliki hubungan signifikan dengan kepatuhan perawat, menandakan pentingnya mempertimbangkan faktor-faktor ini dalam meningkatkan kualitas pelayanan dan keselamatan pasien di instalasi

3. Yuni Sukma Panca Indrawati, Yunita Sari, Annas Sumeru (2023)	Faktor-Faktor yang Memengaruhi Kepatuhan Perawat Terhadap Standar Operasional Prosedur (Sop) Perioperatif Untuk Mencegah Infeksi Luka Post Operasi di RSUD Dr. R. Goeteng Taroenadibrata Purbalingga	Jenis penelitian ini adalah analisis korelasi dengan pendekatan <i>cross sectional</i>	Medikal dan Surgikal rumah sakit Hasil penelitian menunjukkan faktor pengetahuan, masa kerja, peran kepala ruang memiliki hubungan dengan kepatuhan perawat terhadap SOP perioperatif. Sementara itu, beban kerja menjadi faktor dominan yang dapat memengaruhi kepatuhan perawat dalam menjalankan SOP perioperatif.
4. Irvam Efendi, Milkhatun (2020)	Hubungan Sikap Dengan Kepatuhan Perawat Dalam Pelaksanaan Pencegahan Pasien Jatuh Di Rumah Sakit Umum Milik Daerah Samarinda 2019	Penelitian ini menggunakan metode kuantitatif dengan desain <i>descriptive correlation</i> dengan pendekatan <i>cross sectional</i>	Hasil penelitian ini menunjukan bahwa ada hubungan yang positif dan signifikan sikap dengan kepatuhan perawat dalam pelaksanaan pencegahan pasien jatuh dengan nilai <i>p-value</i> 0,017 yang berarti secara statistik ada hubungan antara sikap dengan kepatuhan perawat dalam pencegahan risiko pasien jatuh di RSUD Samarinda.
5. Wiji Lestari, Sondang Ratnauli Sianturi (2022)	Analisa Pengetahuan, Masa Kerja dan Pendidikan dengan Kepatuhan Perawat dalam Pelaksanaan SPO Pasien Resiko Jatuh	Penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan kuantitatif, metode <i>cross sectional</i> dan analisa korelasi deskriptif. Sampel penelitian 118 perawat pelaksana menggunakan teknik <i>purposive sampling</i>	Penelitian ini menyimpulkan bahwa terdapat hubungan antara pengetahuan dengan kepatuhan perawat dalam pelaksanaan standar operasional prosedur risiko jatuh dengan nilai <i>p-value</i> = 0,008 ($p < 0,05$), tidak ada hubungan masa kerja dengan kepatuhan perawat dalam pelaksanaan standar operasional prosedur risiko jatuh dengan nilai <i>p-value</i> = 0,083 ($p > 0,05$) dan ada hubungan pendidikan dengan kepatuhan perawat dalam pelaksanaan standar operasional prosedur

6.	Nada Rizky Dwi Faridha, Milkhatun (2020)	Hubungan dengan Perawat Pelaksanaan Pencegahan Pasien Jatuh di Rumah Sakit Umum Daerah Pemerintah Samarinda	Pengetahuan Kepatuhan dalam Pencegahan Rumah Daerah	Metode yang digunakan deskriptif korelasi dengan pendekatan cross sectional. Instrumen yang digunakan dalam penelitian ini adalah kuisioner dan lembar observasi. Jumlah sampel 51 perawat di ruang rawat inap non intensif dengan teknik pengambilan sampel menggunakan purposive sampling.	risiko jatuh dengan nilai p -value = 0,001 ($p < 0,05$). Hasil analisis menunjukkan p value 0,038 < α (0,05). Terdapat hubungan yang signifikan antara pengetahuan dengan kepatuhan perawat dalam pelaksanaan pencegahan pasien jatuh
----	--	---	---	--	--

Nursing is recognized as a professional, humanistic service that applies a holistic approach, grounded in nursing science and skills, and oriented toward the objective needs of patients (Mardiono *et al.*, 2022). It constitutes an essential component of the healthcare system, providing services to individuals, families, and communities—whether healthy or ill—based on nursing knowledge and techniques (Kemenkes RI, 2019). According to Article 16 of Ministerial Regulation No. 26 of 2019, nurses are expected to fulfill several professional roles, including:

- a. Nursing Care Provider
- b. Counselor and Counselor for Clients
- c. Nursing Service Manager
- d. Nursing Researcher
- e. Task Executor based on delegation of authority
- f. Task Executor in certain limited circumstances

A key responsibility reflecting professional integrity is adherence to standard operational procedures, especially in the context of fall risk prevention. To evaluate how effectively nurses fulfill this role, it is essential to examine various factors influencing their compliance with fall prevention standard operational procedures (Nasution, 2021). Standard operational procedures are structured to standardize nursing practices, ensuring consistent care delivery and guiding nurses—particularly newly assigned staff—toward patient-centered approaches. These protocols also support patient communication about procedures when necessary (Sihura *et al.*, 2022).

A synthesis of 6 selected studies reveals that all used a quantitative cross-sectional design, with nurse participants working in hospitals across Indonesia. Statistical results demonstrate significant correlations between several variables and nurse compliance.

The results of this study showed a p value = (0,006) < α (0,05) (Fatonah *et al.*, 2023) and p value = 0,017 (Efendi and Milkhatun, 2020) which means that statistically there is a relationship between attitudes and nurse compliance in implementing standard operational procedures for preventing fall risks. Research conducted by Mardiono *et al.*, (2022) The results of the chi-square statistical test obtained a value of ρ = 0.001 which is smaller than α = 0.05 which indicates a significant relationship between attitudes towards preventing fall risks in patients. Attitude is a very important thing that a nurse must have. A nurse who has a positive attitude, then the nurse is expected to be able to carry out all his duties effectively and efficiently, so that his performance will increase. In addition, nurses who have a good attitude can be more responsible for what has been chosen with all kinds of risks that exist (Fatonah *et al.*, 2023).

The results of the study showed that the level of education had an effect on nurses' compliance in implementing standard operational procedures for preventing patients at risk of falling with a p -value 0,015 $p < \alpha$ (0,05) so H_0 was rejected (Fatonah *et al.*, 2023). The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Lestari and Sianturi, (2022) using bivariate analysis obtained a p value = 0.001. This means that there is a relationship between education and nurses' compliance in implementing standard operational procedures for preventing patients at risk of falling. Nurses with a bachelor's degree have lecture time with deeper theoretical and practical concepts regarding nursing care and understand the

importance of implementing standard operational procedures while D3 education has less lecture and practice time, besides being more prepared in depth for work practices in the field so that it is considered less in-depth in theory. Thus, the researcher concluded that there is a relationship between education and nurses' compliance with the implementation of standard operational procedures for preventing the risk of falling (Lestari and Sianturi, 2022).

The results of a study by Indrawati *et al.*, (2023) showed that knowledge influences nurses' compliance in implementing standard operational procedures for preventing patients at risk of falling with a p-value of 0.029 which is in line with the results of a study by Faridha and Milkhatun, (2020) and Aprisunadi *et al.*, (2023) that nurses who have good knowledge have a 4.4 times greater chance of complying with implementing prevention of patients at risk of falling compared to nurses who have sufficient knowledge (Aprisunadi *et al.*, 2023). Nurses' knowledge of standard operational procedures is very important in every field where nurses work. In addition to knowing the standard operational procedures for falling risks, nurses must also comply with the standard operational procedures for preventing falling risks to avoid and minimize the incidence of falls in patients so that no additional health problems will arise that will be experienced by patients (Rifai *et al.*, 2021).

Research by Alfisenna *et al.*, (2024) stated that age can affect nurses' compliance in implementing standard operational procedures for preventing patients at risk of falling with a p-value of 0.047. Research by Furroidah *et al.*, (2023) supports this finding by showing that productive-age nurses have better physical conditions and minimal health problems, so they are able to handle heavy tasks more efficiently. In addition, young nurses adapt more quickly to new technologies and procedures, have high energy and motivation to develop, and get more opportunities for further training and education. Meanwhile, older nurses often face decreased productivity due to health problems and decreased physical function, which reduces their work efficiency (Saprudin *et al.*, 2021).

Health service infrastructure is the availability of adequate health facilities so that it can support an adequate service system in a study conducted by Alfisenna *et al.*, (2024) with a p-value of 0.045 which assumes that if nurses feel that the availability of facilities and infrastructure is inadequate or still ineffective in preventing patients at risk of falling, then nurses will feel less motivated in carrying out procedures related to the risk of falling. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Satriani *et al.*, (2025) which shows that nurses who feel their facilities are adequate also have higher work motivation. Thus, it is important for hospitals to ensure adequate fall risk prevention facilities in order to increase nurse compliance and ultimately improve overall patient safety.

The results of the study showed that workload can affect nurses' compliance in implementing standard operational procedures for preventing patients at risk of falling, as evidenced by the results of the p-value= 0.002 (Indrawati *et al.*, 2023). Another study conducted by Puspita *et al.*, (2020) stated that nurses will carry out their duties seriously to achieve optimal performance. The results of the study by Saprudin *et al.*, (2021) statistical tests using the Chi-Square test obtained a p-value = 0.001 ($\alpha < 0.05$) meaning that there is a relationship between workload and efforts to prevent the risk of falling. There is a balance between the number of nurses and the number of patients and also most patients are classified as self-care (Ananta and Dirdjo, 2021) namely patients who can do their own personal hygiene, bathe and change clothes, eat and drink. However, patients need to be supervised when ambulating or moving (Saprudin *et al.*, 2021).

The results of the study stated that long working hours can affect nurses' compliance in implementing fall prevention standard operational procedures. This statement is supported by the results of research conducted by Fatonah *et al.*, (2023) and Indrawati *et al.*, (2023) which shows that there is a significant relationship between the length of work or working hours of nurses with the prevention of patients at risk of falling. This shows that long working hours indicate a positive work experience, one of which is increased compliance with fall risk management. (Rahmaniah *et al.*, 2020). Research conducted by Wijayanti *et al.*, (2022) shows that long working hours indicate more work experience compared to other colleagues. However, this is different from the research results from Lestari and Sianturi, (2022) which states that there is no relationship between length of work and nurse compliance in implementing standard operational procedures for preventing patients at risk of falling. Further research related to nurses' working hours is needed to determine what factors can affect working hours and nurse compliance in implementing standard operational procedures for preventing patients at risk of falling.

Furthermore, there is a significant relationship between the role of the head of the room and nurse compliance in implementing standard operational procedures (p=0,011) (Indrawati *et al.*, 2023). The results of previous research also showed the same results, namely that there is a relationship between the role of the head of the room and nurse compliance in implementing fall risk prevention (Permatasari and Anisah, 2022) The head of the room in carrying out his role in implementing standard operational procedures socialization needs to see the knowledge of his nurses about patient safety standard operational procedures, so that when nurses provide nursing care to patients in accordance with standard procedures

and also avoid unwanted incidents. The head of the room must also routinely monitor what has been socialized to the implementing nurses.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study indicate that nurses' compliance with standard operational procedures for fall risk prevention is influenced by multiple factors, including attitude, educational background, knowledge level, age, workload, length of work experience, availability of healthcare facilities, and the role of the head nurse. Nurses who demonstrate a positive attitude, possess higher education, and have adequate knowledge tend to show greater adherence to established protocols. Those in the productive age range are generally more adaptable and efficient. Furthermore, balanced workloads, supportive infrastructure, and strong supervisory roles from head nurses contribute positively to standard operational procedures implementation. In light of these findings, hospital management is advised to strengthen ongoing training and educational programs, implement equitable workload distribution systems, ensure adequate provision of necessary facilities, and enhance the supervisory and mentoring roles of head nurses. Such measures are expected to foster greater compliance among nursing staff and promote sustained patient safety practices.

LIMITATION

This study has several limitations. The literature review is limited to several databases such as Google Scholar, Garuda Journal, and semantic scholar. So some other relevant studies may be missed. Most of the studies used cross-sectional methods, so it is difficult to know whether these factors really cause changes in nurses' compliance. Finally, most of the studies focused on general factors, so it is important to re-examine the factors that affect nurses' compliance with standard operating procedures to prevent patient falls.

REFERENCES

- Alfisenna, Erwin and Rizka, Y. (2024) 'Jurnal Riset Kesehatan Modern FAKTOR-FAKTOR YANG MEMPENGARUHI KEPATUHAN Jurnal Riset Kesehatan Modern', 6(4), pp. 17–32.
- Ananta, P.G. and Dirdjo, M.M. (2021) 'Hubungan antara beban kerja dengan kinerja perawat di rumah sakit: suatu literature review', *Borneo student research*, 2(2), p. 929. Available at: <https://journals.umkt.ac.id/index.php/bsr/article/download/1565/784>.
- Aprisunadi, A. et al. (2023) 'Hubungan Pengetahuan Dengan Kepatuhan Perawat Dalam Melaksanakan Standar Prosedur Operasional Pencegahan Risiko Jatuh', *Jurnal Persatuan Perawat Nasional Indonesia (JPPNI)*, 8(2), p. 131. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.32419/jppni.v8i2.448>.
- BPK RI (2009) *UNDANG-UNDANG REPUBLIK INDONESIA NOMOR 44 TAHUN 2009 TENTANG RUMAH SAKIT DENGAN, UNDANG-UNDANG REPUBLIK INDONESIA NOMOR 44 TAHUN 2009 TENTANG RUMAH SAKIT DENGAN*. Available at: [https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Download/28118/UU Nomor 44 Tahun 2009.pdf](https://peraturan.bpk.go.id/Download/28118/UU%20Nomor%2044%20Tahun%202009.pdf).
- Efendi, I. and Milkhatun (2020) 'Hubungan Sikap Dengan Kepatuhan Perawat Dalam Pelaksanaan Pencegahan Pasien Jatuh Di Rumah Sakit Umum Milik Daerah Samarinda 2019', *This research can be applied as a reference material in improving health science, especially for nurses and nursing students*, 1(3), pp. 1316–1319.
- Fajarini, Paramarta, V. and Purwanda, E. (2024) 'ANALISIS KEPATUHAN PERAWAT DALAM PELAKSANAAN PROGRAM MANAJEMEN PASIEN DENGAN RISIKO JATUH DI RUMAH SAKIT', *Jurnal Review Pendidikan dan Pengajaran*, 7, pp. 13490–13501. Available at: <https://journal.universitaspahlawan.ac.id/index.php/jrpp/article/view/34705/23019>.
- Faridha, N.R.D. and Milkhatun (2020) 'Hubungan pengetahuan dengan kepatuhan perawat dalam pelaksanaan pencegahan pasien jatuh di rumah sakit umum daerah pemerintah samarinda', *Borneo Student Research*, 1(3), pp. 1883–1889. Available at: <https://journals.umkt.ac.id/index.php/bsr/article/view/886>.
- Fatonah, S., Manurung, I. and Aulia, A.P.P. (2023) 'Faktor-Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Kepatuhan Perawat Dalam Melaksanakan Standar Prosedur Oprasional Pencegahan Risiko Jatuh Di Rsud Dr.H. Abdul Moeloek Provinsi Lampung', *Jurnal Ilmu Keperawatan Indonesia (JIKPI)*, 4(2), pp. 227–235. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.57084/jikpi.v4i2.1324>.
- Furroidah, F., Maulidia, R. and Maria, L. (2023) 'Hubungan Karakteristik Perawat Dengan Tingkat Kepatuhan Dalam Menerapkan Pendokumentasian Asuhan Keperawatan', *Jurnal Ilmiah Kesehatan Media Husada*, 12(1), pp. 26–38. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.33475/jikmh.v12i1.314>.
- Indrawati, Y.S.P., Sari, Y. and Sumeru, A. (2023) 'Faktor-Faktor Yang Memengaruhi Kepatuhan Perawat terhadap Standar Operasional Prosedur (SOP) Perioperatif untuk Mencegah Infeksi Luka Post Operasi di RSUD Dr. R. Goeteng Taroenadibrata Purbalingga', *Journal of Bionursing*, 5(2), pp. 138–

149. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.20884/1.bion.2023.5.2.205>.
- Kemendes RI (2019) *PERATURAN MENTERI KESEHATAN REPUBLIK INDONESIA NOMOR 26 TAHUN 2019 TENTANG PERATURAN PELAKSANAAN UNDANG-UNDANG NOMOR 38 TAHUN 2014 TENTANG KEPERAWATAN*, Kemendes RI. Available at: http://scioteca.caf.com/bitstream/handle/123456789/1091/RED2017-Eng-8ene.pdf?sequence=12&isAllowed=y%0Ahttp://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.regsciurbeco.2008.06.005%0Ahttps://www.researchgate.net/publication/305320484_SISTEM_PEMBETUNGAN_TERPUSAT_STRATEGI_MELESTARI.
- Lestari, W. and Sianturi, S.R. (2022) 'Analisa Pengetahuan, Masa Kerja dan Pendidikan dengan Kepatuhan Perawat dalam Pelaksanaan SPO Pasien Resiko Jatuh', 5(10), pp. 1240-1246.
- Mardiono, S., Alkhusari and Saputra, A.U. (2022) 'Hubungan Pengetahuan Dan Sikap Perawat Terhadap Pencegahan Resiko Jatuh Pada Pasien', *Indonesian Journal Of Health and Medical*, 2(1), pp. 22-32. Available at: <http://ijohm.rcipublisher.org/index.php/ijohm>.
- Nasution (2021) 'Proses Keperawatan dalam Asuhan Keperawatan', *Menentukan Proses Keperawatan Dalam Asuhan Keperawatan*, 1, p. 11. Available at: <https://osf.io/6qfmc>.
- Permatasari, L. and Anisah, S. (2022) 'Hubungan Peran Dan Fungsi Kepala Ruangan Dalam Sosialisasi SPO Identifikasi Pasien Dan Pencegahan Risiko Jatuh Terhadap Insiden Keselamatan Pasien Di RsTaman Harapan BaruTahun2022', *Jurnal Pendidikan dan Konseling*, 4(3), pp. 2298-2307. Available at: <https://journal.universitaspahlawan.ac.id/index.php/jpdk/article/view/5068>.
- Puspita, E.H., Oktariani, M. and Rizqiea, N.S. (2020) 'Hubungan Beban Kerja Perawat Dengan Pencegahan Infeksi Nosokomial Di Ruang Rawat Inap Rsud Simo Boyolali', *Naskah Publikasi*, 63, pp. 1-15.
- Rahmaniah, L., Rizany, I. and Setiawan, H. (2020) 'Hubungan Penjadwalan Dinas Perawat dengan Kepuasan Kerja Perawat di Instalasi Rawat Inap', *Jurnal Kepemimpinan dan Manajemen Keperawatan*, 3(1), p. 29. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.32584/jkkm.v3i1.554>.
- Rifai, A. et al. (2021) 'Pengetahuan dan Sikap Perawat Tentang Kode Etik Keperawatan', *THE JOURNAL OF Nursing Management Issues*, 1(1), pp. 10-17.
- Sancka Stella Ganiada Sihura et al. (2022) 'Analisis Standar Operasional Prosedur Pelaksanaan Ronde Keperawatan', *Journal of Management Nursing*, 1(02), pp. 64-67. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.53801/jmn.v1i02.26>.
- Saprudin, N., Nengsih, N.A. and Asyiyani, L.N. (2021) 'Analisis Faktor Yang Berhubungan Dengan Upaya Pencegahan Risiko Jatuh Pada Pasien Di Kabupaten Kuningan', *Jurnal Kampus STIKES YPIB Majalengka*, 9(2), pp. 180-193. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.51997/jk.v9i2.138>.
- Satriani, Gustina, E. and Zaman, C. (2025) 'ANALISIS KEPATUHAN TENAGA MEDIS DI RUANG RAWAT INAP DALAM MELAKUKAN HAND HYGIENE', 10, pp. 131-147.
- Wijayanti, Nabhani and Win Andrian (2022) 'Gambaran Pengetahuan Risiko Jatuh Dan Kepatuhan Perawat Tentang Manajemen Risiko Jatuh', *Jurnal Ilmiah Kedokteran dan Kesehatan*, 1(2), pp. 98-103. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.55606/klinik.v1i2.717>.